

The Sounds of the English Language and Nepali Language

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Abstract

This article presents an observational overview of the English and Nepali sound systems, how the sounds are produced, their distinctive features, classification and distributional limitations. It also depicts interlingual comparison and contrast between English and Nepali sounds. The sounds of English and Nepali are presented in tables explicitly. The syllable structures of both languages are also mentioned with examples to distinguish the potential sequences of sounds in the two languages within a syllable.

Keywords: Sounds, vowels and consonants, monophthongs and diphthongs, voiced and voiceless, aspiration, syllable

Introduction

Sounds are the building blocks of a Language. They are the meaningful, minimal distinctive units of a language. Longer utterances in a language are constructed by arranging the sounds in an order.

Organs Involved in Producing Speech Sounds

Speech sounds are produced by our organs, which are commonly known as the organs of speech. But there is no organ of our body which is specifically designed for talking. They have other duties to perform biologically, like breathing, smelling, biting, chewing, tasting, swallowing, sucking and other such activities, which are considered to be primary (Abercrombie, 1967). More than half of the human body, from the head to the abdomen, is needed for the production of speech sounds. These bodily organs lie in three groups. One group lies in the trunk, second in the throat and third in the head, which in turn form the respiratory system, the phonatory system, and the articulatory system respectively (ibid.). These organs work together as a unified whole to produce speech sounds. Although not usually identified, we can also involve the ears as organs of speech because they are the main organ of reception of speech sounds.

How Speech Sounds are Produced?

Speech organs are involved in different ways to produce speech sounds, modulating the air in some ways. An air stream is the basis for the whole of the production of sounds. The organs of our body, which are called the initiators, set an air-stream in motion, and the speech organs modulate the air-stream to produce different sounds. Three main types of air-stream mechanisms, viz., pulmonic, glottalic and velaric, are used in human speech. These three mechanisms may be used to push air out or to pull it in. If the air is pushed out, it is called an egressive air-stream, and the reverse is ingressive. The pulmonic air-stream mechanism uses the lungs and respiratory muscles as the initiators. The larynx itself, with the glottis firmly closed, is the initiator in the glottalic air-stream mechanism. The larynx acts exactly as a plunger in a syringe: when moved downwards, it draws the air after it; and when moved upwards, it pushes air out (Abercrombie, 1967). The air it sets in motion is the air in the pharynx, and thus it is also called the pharyngeal air stream mechanism, especially in America. The air below the larynx, in the trachea, bronchial tubes and lungs is not affected and takes no part in the air stream. In the velaric air-stream mechanism, the back part of the tongue is lifted up so that it comes firmly into contact with the velum, which is the initiator. It (contact) is pushed forward in the mouth to

make an egressive air-stream and pulled back to make an ingressive air stream (ibid.). It sets only the air in the mouth in motion. Velaric egressive sounds are not noticed and recorded (in any language) yet.

Nepali and English sounds

In any language, we can identify a small number of regularly used sounds, viz., vowels, which are produced without any obstruction along the supraglottal cavity and consonants, which are produced with complete or partial closure along the supraglottal cavity. These sounds of a language are called phonemes. All human beings are alike, yet every human being has a unique set of fingerprints. In a similar way, all languages make use of consonants and vowels, yet no two languages have the same set of distinct sounds or phonemes (Todd, 1999).

All English and Nepali sounds (phonemes) are produced with a pulmonic egressive air stream mechanism. But the articulators meet or come close at different points and in different manners while producing different sounds of these languages. Vocal cords only and aspiration play an important role in distinguishing some of the sounds from the other sounds between English and Nepali.

The vocal cords are the two small bands of elastic tissue lying opposite each other across the air passage (O'Connor, 1992, p. 13), and the glottis is the space between them. To quote Giegerich (1995, p. 2), "This is where the process of phonation takes place". The vocal cords lie as a pair of lips placed from front to back horizontally across the top of the windpipe. They are joined in the front but movable in such a way that they can either be brought together into contact or pulled apart to form a V-shaped opening from the windpipe into the throat or pharynx. Mainly in the production of English and Nepali sounds, the vocal cords are drawn wide apart, and air passes quite freely in the production of voiceless sounds, or they are brought into contact, and the air makes the vocal cords vibrate deliberately when air passes out in the production of voiced sounds. We can clearly feel the vibration while producing the voiced sounds. If we stop our ears with our fingers while producing the voiced sounds, we can hear or feel a quite distinctive buzzing noise inside the head (Abercrombie, 1967).

Aspiration is the audible breath or the little puff of air that accompanies a sound's articulation. It plays a role in the production of English and Nepali consonant sounds, which are allophonic in the former but phonemic in the latter. In other words, aspirated and unaspirated counterparts of a sound with the same place and manner of articulation and voicing are the allophones of a phoneme in English, but they are distinctive phonemes in Nepali. We can feel aspiration with the help of a leaf of paper held loosely opposite our mouth. In the production of aspirated sounds, the paper moves deliberately which is not noticeable in the production of unaspirated sounds (ibid.).

English and Nepali consonants and vowels are discussed in the following titles observationally.

Vowels

Both English and Nepali vowels are produced with the vibration of the vocal cords, i.e., they are voiced sounds. They are produced with voiced air passing through different mouth shapes. The difference in the shape of the mouth is caused by the different position of the tongue and the lips. The number and quality of English and Nepali vowel sounds vary. To find out their similarities and differences, let us observe them separately.

English Vowels

English vowels are mainly classified into monophthongs and diphthongs. Monophthongs are simple and pure vowels. They can be distinguished as short and long in quality. They are 12 in number. Diphthongs are gliding vowels. A diphthong is a glide from a pure vowel to another, and the whole glide acts like one of the long simple vowels. They are eight in number.

Monophthongs

The vowels of any language can be plotted using the cardinal vowels as a guide. English monophthongs thus can be plotted in a cardinal vowel diagram, in the following way:

English monophthongs plotted in the above diagram are mentioned below with example words.

1. i: - beat, mean, peace, see
2. ɪ - bit, pin, fish, city, sit,
3. e - egg, get, bet, men, yes
4. æ - add, sat, bat, man, gas
5. ɑ: - art, far, card, half, pass
6. ɒ - on, pot, gone, dog, cross,
7. ɔ: - all, raw, board, torn, horse

8. ʊ - put, push, pull, to, good
9. u: - food, soon, loose, ooze, too
10. ʌ - up, but, some, rush, bud
11. ɜ: - church, sir, bird, fern, purse
12. ə - ago, again, about, oppose, perhaps

Among the monophthongs i:, ɜ:, a:, ɔ:, and u: are long vowels and ɪ, e, æ, ɒ, ʊ, ʌ, and ə (which is also called 'schwa' vowel) are short vowels; ʊ, u:, and ɔ: are produced with rounded lips α:, ʌ, ɜ: and ə with neutral lips and i:, ɪ, e, and æ with spread lips. English vowels æ, ɒ, and ʌ do not occur word-finally.

Diphthongs

There are eight diphthongs in English. They can be divided as in this diagram with example words (Roach, 2008, p. 21):

English diphthongs can be shown in the cardinal vowel quadrilateral in this way:

Nepali Vowels

Nepali vowels are mainly monophthongs. However, diphthongs and nasalized vowels are also identified. They are described below:

Monophthongs

There are six pure vowels in Nepali. They are short and simple vowels. We can tentatively plot Nepali vowels in the cardinal vowel quadrilateral in this way (Adhikari, 2006; Gyanwali & Bgattarai, 2008):

Nepali vowels potted above in the cardinal vowel diagram are mentioned below with example words:

1. ɪ – ɪnar (well), ɪman (honesty)
2. e – ek (one), khele (played)
3. a – ama (mother), khana (food)
4. ʌ – ʌchel (nowadays), mʌhan (great)
5. ɔ - ɔkhar (walnut), dhɔka (door)
6. ʊ – ʊkhu (sugarcane), ʊmalnu (boil)

Among these six vowels in Nepali, ʊ and ɔ are rounded, and ɪ, e, a, and ʌ are unrounded according to the position of the lips.

Diphthongs

Generally, we do not notice Nepali diphthongs very easily. But there are some sequences of vowels in Nepali, which occur frequently in speech (Adhikari, 2006, p. 6), called diphthongs. Some sequences of vowels like ɪɪ as in gɪɪnɪ (I did not go), bhɪɪnɪ (I did not become); aɪ as in bhɪ (brother), bhɪnar (statement); ʊɪ as in shʊɪ (niddle), dʊɪ (two); eɪ as in keɪ (some), teɪ (that one); ɔɪ as in pɔɪ (husband), khɔɪ (where is); ʌʊ as in ɕʌʊ (field), gʌʊ (wheat); aʊ as in daʊ (opportunity), bhʌʊ (cost); ɪʊ as in ghɪʊ (ghee), jɪʊ (body); eʊ as in eʊta (one/single), deʊta (God); ɔʊ as in dhɔʊ (wash), chɔʊ (touch) are heard as single vowel. So, they are diphthongs. Among them, eɪ and ʌʊ are easily noticed.

Nasalized Vowels

Nasalization is frequent, and it is phonemic in Nepali vowels. If so, there are an equal number of potential vowels (nasalized vowels) in the Nepali language. For example, ʌ and ɫ̃ (yes), a (come) and ɶ̃ (opening of mouth), bas (shelter) and bɶ̃s (bamboo), gʌe (they went) and gɫ̃e (I went), janchʌʊ (you go) and janchɫ̃ʊ (we go) and many more.

Comparison and Contrast Between the Vowels of English and Nepali

- English has 20 vowels: 12 monophthongs and eight diphthongs.
- Nepali has six pure vowels and ten diphthongs, and perhaps an equal number of nasalized vowels.
- All Nepali vowels occur in all positions, but English vowels **æ**, **ɒ** and **ʌ** do not occur word finally.
- Nasalization is allophonic in English vowels, but it is phonemic in Nepali.
- English has 12 different pure vowels. Thus, it is difficult for Nepali learners to learn English vowels.

Consonants

Consonant sounds are made by a closure or narrowing in the vocal tract so that the airflow is either completely blocked or so restricted that audible friction is produced. English and Nepali consonant sounds are produced when the air stream from the lungs is either completely blocked or partially blocked, or where the opening is so narrow that the air escapes with audible friction or airstream blocked in the mouth but escapes through the nose. English and Nepali consonant sounds are described in short below:

English Consonants

English has 24 consonant sounds. Among them 15 are voiced and nine are voiceless. Aspiration is not phonemic in English. English consonant sounds (in BBC English) can be placed in IPA chart as follows:

Manner of articulation	Place of articulation							
	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Dental	Alveolar	Palato-alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Glottal
Plosive	p b			t d			k g	
Nasal	m			n			ŋ	
Fricative		f v	θ ð	s z	ʃ ʒ			h
Affricate					tʃ dʒ			
Lateral				l				
Frictionless continuant				r				
Semi-vowel/ approximant	w					j		

Note: each symbol on the left refers voiceless and, on the right, refers voiced sound in each box

Among these consonant sounds in English, m, n and l sounds can be syllabic as in person /psɜ:n/, rhythm /rɪðm/ and cattle /kætl/. Similarly, ʒ and ŋ sounds do not occur word-finally. It is also said that there are as many h sounds in English as there are vowels because h always occurs before a vowel.

Nepali Consonants

Nepali has 29 consonant sounds. Among them, 18 sounds are voiced, and 11 sounds are voiceless. Aspiration is phonemic in Nepali. Out of 29 consonants, 12 sounds are aspirated, and 17 sounds are unaspirated. Nepali Sounds can be placed in the IPA chart as follows:

Manner of articulation	Place of articulation					
	Bilabial	Dental	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Glottal
Plosive	P b	t d	ʈ ɖ		k g	
	ph bh	th dh	ʈh ɖh		kh gh	
Nasal	m		n		ŋ	
Fricative			ʃ			h
Affricate			tʃ dʒ			
			ʧ ʝ			
Lateral			l			
Trill			r			
Semi-vowel/ approximant	w			y		

Note: each symbol on the left is voiceless, on the right is voiced; on the top is unaspirated and on the bottom is aspirated sound in each box.

In Nepali- ‘h’ sound is noticeable in the initial position but not word medially and finally as in thaha → thaa (notice), बहिनी → बनिनी (sister), राहे → राए (remained /left). Similarly, ŋ sound is not found word-initially except in some onomatopoeic words and y and w sounds are usually not found word-finally (Sthapit, 1999).

Comparison and contrast between the consonant sounds of English and Nepali

- English has 24 consonant sounds while Nepali has 29 consonant sounds.
- English consonants m, n, l, can be syllabic, but Nepali syllabic consonant sounds are generally not found.
- Both Languages have similar, almost the same nasal consonant sounds m, n and ŋ.
- Aspiration is allophonic in English but phonemic in Nepali.
- Nepali has only two fricative sounds, both aspirated, viz. ʃ and h, the former alveolar voiceless and the latter glottal voiced. But English has nine fricative sounds, five voiceless and four voiced. h is voiceless in English.
- English has six plosive sounds, but Nepali has 16 plosive sounds.
- English has two affricate sounds, but Nepali has four affricate sounds.

Conclusion

The English and Nepali languages have different syllable structures. C₀₋₃ V C₀₋₄ is the potential syllable structure in English, as in I... students, etc. Minimal syllable structure is V as in eye; most

common syllable structure is CV and CVC as in my and rice; syllable structure with maximum onset is CCCVC as in scream, and syllable structure with maximum coda is CVCCCC as in texts.

The potential syllable structure in Nepali is C₀₋₃ V C₀₋₂, as in a (come)... phlyat, blyang (the onomatopoeic words), etc. Minimal syllable structure is V as in a (come); the most common syllable structure is CV as in kha (eat) and CVC as in bhān (say); syllable structure with maximum onset is CCCV as in strī (female), and syllable structure with maximum coda is CVCC as in anānd (Anand), nepalgānj (Nepalgunj). But this is only found in some nouns or some loanwords (Sthapit, 1999).

If we find two sounds similar in some ways in two different languages, we decide that they are the same. But they may be different in essence. They may just seem like the twins, yet their fingerprints in their use are obviously different. The sounds of a language must be learnt in context. Sounds alone cannot be practised and learnt very well.

Symbols and diacritic marks used in this article (especially for the Nepali Sounds)

:	long	˜	nasalization										
P	प्	b	ब्	ph	फ्	bh	भ्	t	त	d	द्	th	थ्
dh	ध्	t̪	ट्	d̪	ड्	th̪	ठ्	ɖh	ढ्	k	क्	g	ग्
kh	ख्	gh	घ्	c	च्	j	ज्	ch	छ्	jh	झ्		
m	म्	n	न्	ŋ	ङ्	sh	श्	h	ह्	l	ल्	r	र्
w	व्	y	य्	ʌ	अ	a	आ	ɪ	इ	ʊ	उ	ɒ	ओ
e	ए	ʌɪ	अइ	aɪ	आइ	ʊɪ	उइ	eɪ	एइ	ɒɪ	ओइ	ʌʊ	अउ
aʊ	आउ	ɪʊ	इउ	eʊ	एउ	ɒʊ	ओउ	ã	आँ	ĩ	आँ		

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